

Language Learning Strategies for Extroverted and Introverted Children at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Class 2 Asy-Syafi'iyah Kendari City

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Abstract

In the concept of personality, every child is born unique or different. Even identical twins will not have the same personality and physique. It is important to know and understand each child's personality in the language learning received in his classroom through initial reading and writing skills. Language learning is a process that must be understood by all parties directly involved in dealing with these students. This type of research includes qualitative research. Researchers conduct direct research in the field of children in Madrasah Ibtidaiyah class 2A Asy-Syafi'iyah to provide objective data in the form of the personality types of children who are extroverted and introverted in language learning. The sources of data in this study were children, teachers of each field of study, and homeroom teachers of grade 2A, who were considered to be able to provide information. In contrast, the data collection tools or research instruments were the researchers themselves. The findings in this study indicate that children's tendencies towards extroverted or introverted personalities can contribute greatly to children's creative processes in language learning and can help them develop their potential to the fullest, so that language learning is said to be able to use reading and writing skills well, and balanced. This study also shows that children with extroverted personalities tend to be better at learning the language than those with introverted personalities, but developments are occurring. This study provides a different perspective that personality type affects children's language learning abilities, especially reading and writing skills.

Keywords: *Strategy, Language Learning, Extroverted and Introverted Children.*

INTRODUCTION

Language learning in elementary schools or Madrasah Ibtidaiyah has the main place for students because, through language learning, basic language skills are first laid. Some students who enter elementary school do not have the same background. Some are from kindergarten, some are from home, and each child has a different personality. Language learning becomes very important, especially early reading and writing. Anyone living in this world cannot know various kinds of knowledge if they cannot read and write. Without having the ability to read and write from an early age, students will experience learning difficulties later in life or at the next level.

In general, there are two major types of personality in social life. The first is an outgoing person who easily blends in with the surrounding environment, commonly called an extrovert. In contrast, a second type is a person who chooses to interact with certain people and takes a long time to blend in or is called an introvert. Another understanding of extroverted personality is the tendency of a person to direct attention outside himself so that all interests, attitudes, and decisions are more determined by events outside of him. At the same time, introverts are tendencies whose attention is more directed to the inside of them. To his, "*akunya*" means "me," who is less pleasant, quiet, difficult to dive into, likes to be alone, and often afraid of people.

Language learning in elementary schools/madrasah Ibtidaiyah, especially class 2A, is a process that must be understood by all parties who are directly involved in dealing with these students. Through a personality approach, each student can examine the level of ability of each student to understand and master aspects of reading and writing skills during language learning in the classroom. This is reinforced by Hartati's opinion that language learning is closely related and will not be possible to stand alone and at almost the same time will automatically learn letters and write them down.

Based on the researchers' observations in class 2A Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Asy-Syafi'iyah Kendari, with a total of 20 people, data on language learning were obtained as follows 12 students were fluent in reading, and eight students were not fluent in reading. Likewise, in the aspect of writing skills. From this initial observation, the researcher is interested in exploring research by conducting research on language learning through an extroverted and introverted personality approach to each student by looking at their reading and writing skills. So that through this research, it will be known how the student's personality has an impact on mastering reading and writing in language learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of Language Learning

In essence, learning a language is learning to communicate, so there is no integrated communication system, including speech, reading, and writing, but a linguistic system. Every language teaching aims to make students or students have language skills. According to Tarigan, being skilled in language includes four things: skilled in listening, skilled in speaking, skilled in writing, and skilled in reading. The four of them are single chess in teaching Indonesian. These four aspects can be divided into two major groups: receptive skills, which include reading and listening skills, and revealing (productive) skills, including writing and speaking skills.

Writing skills in language learning are delivering messages to other parties in writing. As a process, writing consists of pre-writing, writing, and post-writing stages. Reading skills are the process of delivering written messages from other parties. As a process, reading is a continuous meaning activity based on what is presented in the text and the knowledge possessed by the reader.

For early reading learning, it is given in grades I and II with the aim that students can understand and voice writing with reasonable intonation as a basis for further reading. Beginning reading learning is the level of the process of learning to read to master the writing system as a visual representation of language. This level is often referred to as the level of learning to read. Further reading is the level of the process of mastering reading to obtain the message content contained in writing. This level is called reading to learn. The two levels are a continuum, meaning that at the initial reading level, which focuses on mastering the writing system, advanced reading learning has also begun with even limited understanding. Likewise, advanced reading emphasizes understanding the content of the reading, and it still needs improvement and refinement of mastery of preliminary reading techniques.

Language Learning Strategy

Language is a communication system that uses arbitrary symbols that real body movements can strengthen. A symbol is a sign given a certain meaning, which refers to something absorbed by the five senses. Language has certain characteristics, namely:

1. A set of sounds, the order of which obeys certain rules.
2. It is arbitrary; the relationship between sound and the order of the objects is arbitrary and cannot be guessed.
3. Systematic in nature, each language has a different system from any language system.
4. Language is a set of symbols, language sounds produced by human speech in the form of words, actually symbols that represent an object, process, event, or activity.
5. Perfect, which has fulfilled the speaker's mandate.

Regarding language learning, Kumaradivelu explained that there are procedures in the classroom that teachers need to implement, namely modifying the material and facilitating student interaction activities. A material modification is related to the way the teacher presents material that can make students motivated to learn. In this case, the teacher needs to apply appropriate learning strategies. Interaction activities are related to how the teacher conveys assignments to students to be discussed by providing opportunities for these students to interact with friends through cooperation.

Personality Type

a. Definition of Personality

In English, the word personality comes from the Ancient Greek *Prosopan* or *persona*, which means "*topeng*," usually used by theater artists. The artist behaves according to the mask's expression as if the mask has certain personality traits. So the initial concept of understanding personality (in ordinary people) is behavior placed in a social environment. The impression of self is desired to be captured by the social environment. (Alwisol, 2004)

According to Eysenck (in Alwisol, 2004), personality is the overall pattern of organisms' actual and potential behavior, determined by heredity and environment. The pattern of behavior originates and is developed through the functions of the four main sectors that organize behavior; cognitive sector (intelligence), conative sector (character), affective sector (temperament), and somatic sector (constitution). This is different from the opinion of Yusuf and Nurihsan (2007). They explain that personality is the behavior shown in the social environment, the impression about the self desired to be captured by the social environment.

Based on some of the opinions above, it can be concluded that personality is a totality of typical behavior for individuals who react and adapt to all stimuli, both those that come from their environment (the outside world) and those that come from themselves. In the long term, general or special characteristics inherent in him form themselves into a unit and can function well or badly in themselves and their environment.

b. Personality Theory

The human soul is divided into the ability aspect and the personality aspect. Personality needs to be known and studied because personality is closely related to the pattern of acceptance of the social environment towards a person. People who have a personality under the pattern adopted by the community in their environment will experience a good reception. Still, on the contrary, if a person's personality is not appropriate, especially contrary to the pattern adopted by the environment, there will be rejected by the community.

Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961) was the first to define the type of human personality with the terms extrovert and introvert and described four functions of the human personality called thinking, sensing, intuitive, and feeling functions. Jung's initial motivation for investigating human typology was his desire to understand that Freud's view of mental disorders differed from Adler's. The subject of Jung's study is very distinctive about the archetypes of each event.

Jung, a psychiatrist from Switzerland, divided human types in another way. He was a pupil of Freud, an expert *Diepte Psychologie*. The flow of psychology is called *Analytische Psychologie*. Therefore, in his typology, the unconscious plays an important role. Meanwhile, the basis of Jung's typology is the direction of human attention. He said that human attention is directed in two directions, namely outside of him, which is called extrovert, and inward, which is called an introvert. Where the direction of the human's attention is strongest out or into it is what determines the type of person.

According to Jung, human types can be divided into two major groups, namely:

1. Extroverts are people whose attention is directed outside themselves, other people, and society. People belonging to the extrovert type have the following characteristics: open-hearted, fluent in socializing, friendly, cheerful, and contact with the environment is very large. They are easy to influence and easily influenced by their environment. Describe in more detail the properties of these groups as follows:

Extroverted personality traits, divided:

- a. Extroverted thinking is always using logic and analysis in making decisions and tends to be task-centered and objective, with the following characteristics:
 - Likes to work with other people;
 - It relies on real (definite) thinking;
- b. Feeling extroverted, namely, someone whose attention is directed outside himself and who plays a role in his attention is his feelings, with the following characteristics:
 - Free from his worries or anxieties;
 - Not shy and not awkward;
 - Friendly and gregarious;
 - Lack of concern for the suffering and own property.
- c. Sensing extroverts are processing data by relying on concrete, realistic, and seeing facts as they are, with the following characteristics:
 - Receive stimuli externally in reality.
- d. Extroverted intuition is a subconscious process created from experience, with the following characteristics:
 - Guided by hunches and forecasts;
 - Fact oriented in the external world.

So the extrovert type personality is a person's tendency to direct attention away from him so that events outside him more determine all interests, attitudes, and decisions taken. Generally, they are in tune with the culture and the people around them and try to make decisions according to and under the demands and expectations of the environment.

2. The introvert type is people whose attention is more directed to the inside than the "Aku." People belonging to the introverted type have the following characteristics: less pleasant, quiet, difficult to dive into, like to be alone, and are often afraid of people. Introverted personality traits, divided: More fluent in writing than speaking, Tend to be often overwhelmed with worries, Easily shy and clumsy, Tend to be radical, Likes to read books and magazines, Somewhat introverted, Likes to work alone, Very caring or careful heart towards suffering and its possessions, Difficult to adjust and rigid in socializing.

Extrovert and Introvert Personality Characteristics

Two dimensions of personality type attitude are extrovert and introvert. Extroverts are pleasant, open, and easy to relate to other people. At the same time, introverts are characterized by difficulty getting along, being closed, and having difficulty establishing relationships with other people. The characteristics of extroverts are sociability, friendly, active speaking, impulsive, fun, active, and spontaneous, while the opposite characterizes introverts.

Individuals with extrovert tendencies seem more enthusiastic, pleasant, and impulsive in displaying behavior. At the same time, individuals who tend to be introverted will pay more attention to their thoughts, moods, and reactions. This makes introverted individuals tend to be shy, have strong self-control, and are fixated on what happens to them. In more detail, the description of the components of extroverted and introverted personality types includes activity, sociability, courage to take risks (risk-taking), obedience to impulses (impulsiveness), expression of feelings (expressiveness), depth of thinking (reflectiveness), and responsibility, as can be seen in the following table:

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

i. Language Learning Strategies for Extroverted and Introverted Children in Reading Skills at MI Asy-Syafi'iyah Class 2A

When children start primary school, they must use Indonesian to communicate. Even learning to read and write is done using Indonesian. Meanwhile, the urban vocabulary mastered by grade 2A children is a language with a regional dialect. Therefore, since children enter elementary school, teachers begin to familiarize students with listening and conversing in Indonesian, so vocabulary enrichment and introduction of Indonesian language rules can be done quickly.

Based on the research findings, the following describes one by one the types of reading taught at Madrasah Asy-Shafi'iyah:

a. Reading Technique

Reading techniques are, in principle, the same as reading aloud. It is said to read aloud because this reading activity is carried out with vocalizations. Many experts state the importance of reading aloud. Cox in Gusti Yarni stated that daily reading aloud for students is important to teach them to listen, speak, or write.

Parents who read stories to their children, it turns out that their children get good language development through vocabulary development, high reading enthusiasm, and finally succeed in reading the beginning when they have entered school. Reading this technique is also a reading activity carried out by class 2A teachers, which emphasizes the following mastery.

1. Mastery of pronunciation, which is good and correct.
2. Proper mastery of pauses, songs, and intonation.
3. Mastery of punctuation marks.
4. Mastery of grouping words/phrases into idea units.
5. The mastery of moving the eyes and maintaining eye contact.
6. Mastery of expression.

Based on observations, children in the extrovert category are easier and faster to master reading techniques than introverted children. Extroverted children always read quickly or in a hurry without paying attention to the title or theme because they are sure of the reading. Still, introverted children prefer to read the title or theme first and then enter the reading. Based on existing data, 28 children are fluent in reading, two people spell letters, and five children are new to letters.

According to Curl Jung's theory, based on indicators of extrovert and introvert personality types, in the children of MI Asy-Syafi'iyah Class 2A, out of 28 fluent in reading, there are 18 children in the extrovert category and 10 in the introvert category. For children who are not yet fluent in reading, the attitude is more silent and indifferent when the practice of reading aloud is shown in class.

b. Reading in the Heart

Silent reading is a kind of reading that is done without voicing what is read. Silent reading includes advanced reading subject matter. This means that the material for reading silently began to be given in class III of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah, although the practice was given in class II. Silent reading material aims to get information from a reading by understanding the contents of the reading accurately and carefully.

1. To achieve the goal of reading silently, elementary school students should pay attention to the following:
2. Reading is done without sound, lip movements, and noise.
3. Reading is done without any head movements, nodding, shaking his head because of satisfaction with what he reads, or moving his fingers following the reading.
4. When reading, do not stop at difficult readings for the reader to understand so that the reader only thinks about the difficult readings, all of which will cause the failure to read silently.
5. Readers can concentrate both physically and mentally.

Based on observations, ten children fall into the introvert category preferring the silent reading technique even though this technique is more emphasized in third graders. By reading silently, children with introverted

tendencies need a relatively long time to think because the brain work process of introverted children is indeed more complex and lengthy. This sometimes makes introverted children uncomfortable when they have to study together with other children. This is because introverted children need a longer working time. Sometimes this situation makes them stressed and uncomfortable with the school environment.

To practice reading skills silently, Asy-Syafi'iyah teachers always provide reading exercises or activities by providing materials in magazines, newspapers, or books that students have never read on the sidelines of the children's break. Usually, they use the reading room—Green during recess. The important thing that the Asy-Shafi'iyah Madrasa teachers always pay attention to is that the reading material is adjusted to the age level of the students.

c. Speed Reading

Speed reading is a reading activity that aims to understand the contents of the reading accurately, quickly, and carefully in a relatively short time. Speed reading lessons in elementary school should be free from difficult words, new expressions, or phrases or sentences that are quite complex. If forced in the reading, there are difficult words, new expressions, or complex phrases or sentences, and the teacher should explain them to students first so that students are free from language difficulties.

They are limiting/specifying the number of readings. The second method is different from the first method. Suppose the first method is limited by time, while the number of readings limits the second method. All children are given the same amount of reading material. They are free to read at their own pace. After finishing reading, the reading speed is calculated through the calculations described above. The weakness of this method lies in classical teaching, where the number of children is more than ten students because it is difficult to supervise/control children's reading time.

Based on the research findings, six children are in the extrovert category who can read quickly and well. This is easy to do because these six extroverted children are more open and able to read fluently, although based on observations, sometimes some words are missed when reading fast. Extroverted children prefer new challenges, including in terms of reading and communicating.

d. Reading Language

Reading language aims to increase elementary school students' knowledge of the intricacies of the Indonesian language. The main target of language reading lessons is not on understanding the content of the reading but on the accuracy of using language in reading material.

Based on field observations, only three introverted children can respond to the grammar rules of reading well. However, they are still stammering, including the use of affixes, vocabulary mastery, and others.

e. Beautiful Reading

Beautiful reading is often referred to as emotional reading. It is said so because it involves matters related to beauty or aesthetics that can cause emotions or feelings for readers and listeners. The goal to be achieved in this lesson is that students can get a beauty whose source is language or beauty that comes from reading.

Materials that can be used to teach this beautiful reading can be in the form of poetry, prose, or drama. There are several things that teachers need to pay attention to regarding the selection of literary materials for this beautiful reading, including The material should contain educational values, for example, heroism, humanity, and so on. The sentences or words used by the author are denotative and not connotative. Teachers need to pay attention to things like this because, on average, school/elementary-age children can only grasp the contents of sentences that are concluded in the denotative language in literary works.

Based on observations, three extroverted children and five introverted children can read beautifully with intonation, movement, mimicking, and gesture well in front of the class. This shows that the teacher is still not optimal in providing examples of beautiful reading to children because children still do not like the beautiful reading technique. So far, children still think this beautiful reading is a very simple activity: reading by making a sound or reciting the sound symbols of language in a loud enough voice. The fact that happened in MI Asy-Syafi'iyah Class 2A, the children were not taught how to read the beautiful technique but emphasized that children understand the letters first, which means educating children to recognize and change written symbols into sounds that meaning. Although the target to be achieved by the teacher in beautiful reading is that when the children are already fluent in reading, children will begin to be trained to read beautifully so that reading activities are not for themselves but reading for the benefit of others (listeners) because beautiful reading is a process of communicating the contents of reading. beautifully) to others.

ii. **Language Learning Strategies for Extroverted and Introverted Children in Writing Skills at MI Asy-Syafi'iyah Class 2A**

The ability to write is not acquired naturally but through the teaching and learning process. To be able to write letters as symbols of sound, children begin to learn to practice starting from how to hold a writing utensil. Students also practice moving their hands by paying attention to what to write or draw. Students must be trained to observe the sound symbol and understand each letter as a certain sound-symbol until they write it correctly. To be meaningful, this initial learning process of writing is carried out after students can recognize the letters being taught.

Based on the research findings, several grade 2A children continue writing activities convincingly and enthusiastically as they did in grade I. They produce a story that explains their lives. For extroverted children, writing is an uninteresting activity. A misspelling of a word can cause students to toss the paper before trying to write again. Even a small error mark can cause a child to throw away the paper and start over. Different things happen to introverted students. They rarely worry about their writing because they focus on enjoying writing activities and not looking for reader reactions or spelling mistakes. Thus, the recognition of self-ability began to be seen in grade II.

The implementation of language learning through writing skills in class 2A MI Asy-Syafi'iyah is based on the competencies as stated in the 2006 curriculum as follows:

Beginning writing through story completion and dictation activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Complete the simple story with the right words ➤ Write simple sentences dictated by the teacher using cursive letters and pay attention to the use of capital letters and periods.
Begin writing by describing objects around and copying children's poems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Describing plants or animals around in simple written language ➤ Copying children's poems with neat cursive letters.

In addition, teaching writing in class II still introduces writing with lowercase letters. Teach them sequentially from letters/writings that are easy to pronounce to those that are difficult. Teaching writing in class 2A is different from class I, and the difficulty level is relatively high.

iii. **Factors supporting and inhibiting language learning in extroverted and introverted children at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah class 2A Asy-Syafi'iyah**

Language learning in extroverted and introverted children is one of the areas of basic ability development prepared by teachers to improve children's abilities and creativity according to their developmental stages. Language development aims for children to express their thoughts through simple language appropriately, communicate effectively, and generate interest in being able to speak good and correct Indonesian. Therefore, the supporting and inhibiting factors for children in language learning are:

Supporting factors:

a. Teacher as child guide

Teachers always try to guide children to find their various potential. Based on the results of an interview with the homeroom teacher of class 2A, MI Asy-Syafi'iyah by Mrs. Ummu Hasim, A. Ma. said that the teacher of MI Asy-Syafi'iyah always guides students so that they can achieve and carry out their developmental tasks, so that by With this achievement, he can grow and develop as an independent and productive individual.

Children are unique individuals, meaning that no two individuals are alike. Although they may have similarities physically, they are not the same in terms of talents, interests, abilities, etc. Besides that, every child is also a developing creature. The rhythm of their development is certainly not the same either. It is the difference that the teacher demands to act as a guide.

b. Conducive School Environment

A conducive learning environment is very influential on learning outcomes because learning is an activity that requires high concentration. A comfortable place and environment will make it easier for students to concentrate. By preparing the right environment, students will get better results and enjoy a good learning process.

Obstacle factor:

a. Teacher Education Background

The educational background of teachers at MI Asy-Syafi'iyah is still a major problem. At the school, there are still several teachers with a Bachelor of Science background and not a bachelor of education, so the skills that should be mastered by teachers when teaching are opening and closing lessons, questioning skills, explaining skills, making variations skills, skills providing reinforcement, skills guiding discussions. Small groups, classroom management skills, and small group and individual teaching skills have not been well-formed. With the ability and educational background of the teacher, the teacher easily guides children according to their development and personality type. Moreover, the children of MI Asy-Syafiiyah can already see the tendency of the personality types of extroverted and introverted children with different handling.

b. Guidance and Counseling Teacher

Guidance and counseling teachers are professional educators with minimum academic qualifications of Bachelor of Education in the field of Guidance and Counseling and have competence in the field of guidance and counseling with the task of carrying out guidance and counseling services, namely educating, guiding, and developing students' abilities in solving problems experienced and all potential through guidance and counseling services.

At MI Asy-Syafi'iyah, there is no teacher assigned specifically to each class who acts as a Guidance and Counseling teacher to overcome students who have problems in the teaching and learning process and help students become more independent in participating in learning at school. BK teachers can also work with class teachers in guiding and providing treatment for children with extroverted personality types and introverted children so that class teachers will find it easier in the teaching and learning process according to the handling of each child.

CONCLUSION

The uniqueness of children refers to differences. Each of these differences makes the child achieve different results. In learning, especially language learning, every child has a way to achieve maximum results.

The findings in this study indicate that children's tendencies towards extroverted or introverted personalities can greatly contribute to children's creative language learning processes and help them develop their potential to the fullest, so that language learning is said to be able to use language reading and writing skills well. And they are balanced. This study shows that children with extroverted personalities tend to be better at learning a language than those with introverted personalities, but developments are occurring. This study provides a different perspective that personality type affects children's language learning abilities, especially reading and writing skills.

REFERENCES

1. Anonim, Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia di Kelas Rendah, online, <http://pustaka.ut.ac.id>.
2. Degeng, I.N.S. (1997). *Strategi pembelajaran: Mengorganisasi isi dengan model elaborasi*. Malang: IKIPMalang.
3. Djaali, *Psikologi Pendidikan*, Jakarta, Bumi Aksara, 2008
4. Emzir, *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan Kuantitatif & Kualitatif*, (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2008)
5. Farida, Rahim. *Strategi pembelajaran membaca di SD*. Jakarta: BumiAksara, 2006
6. Gagne, R.M. *Essential of learningfor instruction*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall., 1998
7. Ginsburg, H.P., *Piaget's theory of intelektual development* (3rd ed.). New Jersey: PrenticeHall. 1998
8. Gusti Yarni, *Pendekatan dan Strategi Pembelajaran Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia di SD*, Jurnal Pendidikan Penabur - No.11, Tahun ke-7, Desember 2008
9. Hartati T., Resmini N., & Cahyani L., *Pembinaan Pengembangan Pembelajaran Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia*, Bandung:UPI, 2006
10. Heni Mularsih, *Strategi Pembelajaran, Tipe Kepribadian Hasil Belajar Bahasa Indonesia pada Siswa Sekolah Menengah Pertama*, Makara: Sosial Humaniora, Vol.14, No.1, Juli 2010, 65-74.
11. Hill, A.A. *Introduction to linguistic structures*. New York: Harcourt Brace Javanovich, Inc, 1958
12. Januszewski, A. *Educational technology: The development of a concept*. Englewood, Colorado: Libraries Unlimited, Inc., 2001, h.11
13. Kartono, Kartini, *Peran Keluarga Memandu Anak*. Cet. Ke-2 (Jakarta: Rajawali Press, 1992)
14. Keraf, *Komposisi*. Ende Flores: Nusa Indah, 1993

15. Larsen, D. *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. Second Edition. New York: Axford, 2000
16. Lexy J. Moleong, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2001)
17. M. Ngalim Purwanto, *Psikologi Pendidikan*, Bandung, PT. Rosda Karya, 2011
18. Menyuk, Paula. 1988. *Language Development: Knowledge and Use*. (Glenview, dll: Scott, Foreman and Company)
19. Muchlisoh, *Materi Pokok Bahasa Indonesia 3*, Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 1992
20. Purwoko, Agung, *Kegiatan Belajar Mengajar*. Semarang: UNNES Press, 2001
21. Shultz. D. & Schultz, S.E., *Theories of Personality*, Kaduna: Pacific Groove, 1994
22. Stephan P. Robins, *Prinsip-Prinsip perilaku organisasi*, Jakarta, PT. Erlangga, 2002
23. Subana & Sunarti, *Strategi Belajar Mengajar Bahasa Indonesia*, Bandung: Pustaka Setia, 2005
24. Sugiono, *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2005)
25. Sugiono, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif, Kuantitatif dan R & D*, (Bandung: CV. Alfabeta, 2009)
26. Suryosubroto. *Sistem pengajaran modul*. Jakarta: BinaAksara. 1983
27. Syafi'ie, I. *Pengajaran Membaca di Kelas-Kelas Awal Sekolah Dasar*. Malang: FPBS Universitas Negeri Malang, 1999.
28. William Crain, *Teori Perkembangan: Konsep dan Aplikasi*, (Edisi Bahasa Indonesia), Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar, 2007